

Synthesis of some arylalkoxyphthalimides

Sonal Rajora, Lalit Kumar Baregama and G. L. Talesara*

Department of Chemistry, College of Science, M. L. Sukhadia University, Udaipur-313 001, India

E-mail : gtalesara@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 3 May 1999, revised 30 April 2001, accepted 5 June 2001

Some alkoxy-1*H*-isoindole-1,3(2*H*)-dione derivatives of phenothiazine and indole have been prepared by the action of 2-(bromoalkoxy)-1*H*-isoindole-1,3(2*H*)-dione with the corresponding heterocycles.

Many derivatives of phenothiazine¹ and indole² and many alkoxyphthalimides³ are known for their versatile pharmacological properties. Hence it appeared of interest to us to prepare some arylalkoxyphthalimides involving phenothiazine and indole nuclei (**2a-d**; **3a-d**), the result of which is presented in this communication.

Results and Discussion

Phthalic anhydride was treated with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in presence of aqueous sodium carbonate⁴ to give *N*-hydroxyphthalimide. It was converted to the corresponding 2-bromoalkoxy derivatives (**1**, *n* = 2, 3, 4, 5) by

2a-d; **3a-d**

For **2a-d** Het = 10-Phenothiazinyl

3a-d Het = 1-Indolyl

n = 2 for **a**; 3 for **b**; 4 for **c**; 5 for **d**

reacting with α,ω -dibromoalkanes⁵. Excess of the dibromoalkanes were used to avoid substitution at both ends of the dibromoalkanes. For the preparation of 10-substituted-phenothiazines (**2a-d**), phenothiazine itself was converted

to its sodium salt by refluxing it with NaH in DMSO and then refluxed with **1** to give the products. Alternatively, the condensation was also carried out in presence of K₂CO₃ using ethanol as solvent, but the yields in these cases were poor. Similarly, indole was converted to **2a-d** by stirring with KOH in DMSO, followed by treatment with **1**.

Experimental

All m.ps are uncorrected. Purity of the products was tested by TLC. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1330 spectrophotometer. All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

2-Hydroxy-1*H*-isoindole-1,3(2*H*)-dione⁴ and 2-bromoalkoxy-1*H*-isoindole-1,3(2*H*)-dione (**1**)⁵ were prepared by the reported methods.

N-Phenothiazinylalkoxyphthalimides (**2a-d**) : Phenothiazine (0.01 mol) was stirred with 57% NaH (0.32 mol) in DMSO (30 ml) at 40° for 2 h. A solution of the bromoalkoxyphthalimide (**1**; 0.01 mol) in DMSO (25 ml) was added to it and the mixture was refluxed for 4–11 h. It was then filtered hot and the filtrate was cooled to RT and poured in water (400 ml). The resulting solid products were washed free of alkali, dried and crystallized; **2a** (78%) m.p. 153° (ethanol), ν_{\max} 2860, 1710 (CO–N–CO), 740 cm⁻¹ (C–S–C); *m/z* 388 (34), 212 (47), 198 (100), 184 (53); **b** (65%), 160° (ethanol), ν_{\max} 1735 (CO–N–CO), 755 cm⁻¹ (C–S–C); **c** (75%), 168° (toluene), ν_{\max} 1760 (CO–N–CO), 730 cm⁻¹ (C–S–C); **d** (60%), 172° (ethanol), *m/z* 430 (34), 198 (100), 166 (32).

N-Indolylalkoxyphthalimides (**3a-d**) : A mixture of indole (0.01 mol) and KOH (1.2 g) was stirred in DMSO (30 ml) at RT for 15 min. Then bromoalkoxyphthalimide (**1**; 0.01 mol) was added to it and the stirring continued for 10–15 h. It was then filtered and the filtrate poured in water (250 ml). The solid products were dried, washed free of alkali and crystallized; **3a** (68%), m.p. 113° (ethanol), ν_{\max}

R = *N*-Phthalimido

Scheme 1, Reagents : (i) NH₂OH, aq. NaHCO₃, (ii) Br-(CH₂)_n-Br, TEA, DMF, (iii) NaH, DMSO; phenothiazine, (iv) KOH, DMSO; indole.

1685 (CO–O–CO), 1207 cm^{-1} (N–O); m/z 306 (20), 190 (100), 146 (12), **b** (62%), 121^o (ethanol), m/z 320 (7), 204 (100), 162 (13), 146 (78); **c** (60%), 123^o (ethanol); **b** (65%), 115^o (ethanol).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Head, Department of Chemistry, M. L. Sukhadia University, Udaipur, for facilities and to Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for spectral measurements and elemental analyses.

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